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9 **Short-term dynamics of *Quercus ilex* advance regeneration in a *Pinus nigra* plantation**
10 **after the creation of small canopy gaps**

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12 Sergi Garcia-Barreda^{1,*}, Santiago Reyna^{1,2}

13 ¹Fundación Centro de Estudios Ambientales del Mediterráneo (CEAM). C/ Charles Darwin
14 14 Parque Tecnológico, 46980 Paterna, Valencia, Spain

15 ²ETS Ingeniería Agronómica y del Medio Natural, Universidad Politécnica de Valencia,
16 Camino de Vera s/n, 46022 Valencia, Spain

17 *Corresponding author: sergi@ceam.es, (+34) 96 131 82 27

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19

20 Abstract

21 *Aim of the study:* The aim of the research is to analyse the role of *Quercus ilex* advance
22 regeneration in the stand regeneration of pine plantations after small-sized canopy openings,
23 and to assess the influence of the forest stand and the canopy opening. The performance of the
24 advance regeneration under the pine plantation is also examined.

25 *Area of study:* A *Pinus nigra* plantation in dry Continental Mediterranean climate in eastern
26 Spain.

27 *Materials and Methods:* The tree regeneration of ten canopy openings of 0.17-0.43 ha was
28 monitored during five years after treatment. It was also sampled in 0.12 ha-plots in the non-
29 treated pine plantation surrounding the openings.

30 *Main results:* An important increase in the height of *Q. ilex* regeneration was observed in the
31 openings, unlike what was found in the intact pine plantation. In the pine plantation, stand
32 density showed a moderate positive influence on the density of *Q. ilex* regeneration, whereas
33 in the canopy gaps *Q. ilex* height was negatively influenced by stand density before the
34 opening.

35 *Research highlights:* The canopy opening triggered a response in *Q. ilex* advance regeneration,
36 although height growth rates seemed to reduce over time. The results support the view that
37 promoting *Q. ilex* in pine plantations may require different management strategies depending
38 on the characteristics of the pine overstorey and on the density and size of the advance
39 regeneration.

40

41 Key words: Mediterranean forest, stand initiation, seedling resprout, group selection cutting,
42 truffle

43 1 Introduction

44 The evergreen holm oak (*Quercus ilex* L) forests represent the potential vegetation in more
45 than half of Mediterranean Spain (Maldonado *et al.*, 2002). Their extension is nowadays
46 much more limited, due to the historical spread of agriculture, abusive logging and
47 overgrazing. In the second half of the 20th century the overexploitation was reduced and
48 many of the degraded lands were recolonised or reforested with pines (Ortuño, 1990). In
49 recent decades the decrease in the economic profitability of timber and traditional forest
50 products has led to abandonment of forest management (Domínguez-Torres and Plana, 2002).
51 Several alternative uses have been proposed to promote forest management, like hunting and
52 mushrooms. In lands suitable for the growing of the prized black truffle (*Tuber*
53 *melanosporum* Vitt.) the experts propose to convert pine plantations and shrublands to
54 understocked oak stands in order to improve the habitat for *T. melanosporum* and promote
55 forest profitability (Reyna *et al.*, 2004; Diette and Lauriac, 2005).

56 The plantations of Mediterranean pines are frequently invaded by seedlings of *Q. ilex* (Gómez,
57 2003). Many oak species regenerate through the accumulation of advance regeneration below
58 overstorey (Johnson *et al.*, 2002). The shoot growth of these seedlings is suppressed by adult
59 trees and they often dieback and resprout. Some of these seedlings show a rapid shoot growth
60 when the overstorey is disturbed (Johnson *et al.*, 2002). Retana *et al.* (1999) studied the
61 behaviour of *Q. ilex* seedling under forest canopies and concluded that shade favours seedling
62 emergence and survival during the first year; however, light deficit limits seedling growth and
63 often interacts with water deficit.

64 The role of the advance regeneration of *Q. ilex* in the stand regeneration after canopy
65 disturbance is controversial. In *Q. ilex* coppice forests, Retana *et al.* (1999) and Gracia *et al.*
66 (2001) concluded that its role is minor in the short term, since the advance regeneration did
67 not show release after thinning the overstorey. The stumps resprout vigorously, rapidly out-
68 competing seedlings (Espelta *et al.*, 1999). By contrast, its role in Mediterranean pines stands,
69 which do not resprout, has not been thoroughly examined.

70 In this study, we analyse tree regeneration in a *P. nigra* plantation with *Q. ilex* advance
71 regeneration during the five years after experimental small-sized canopy openings aimed to
72 improve the habitat for *T. melanosporum*, and we focus on the role of the advance
73 regeneration. The influence of the characteristics of the forest stand and the canopy opening
74 on tree regeneration is also assessed, as well as the influence of forest stand characteristics on
75 the advance regeneration under the intact pine plantation.

76

77 2 Materials and methods

78 2.1 Study site

79 The study was conducted in El Toro, Valencian Community, eastern Spain (39°59' to 40°1' N;
80 0°44' to 0°46' W, 990-1050 m a.s.l.). The climate is Continental Mediterranean, with a mean
81 annual rainfall of 500-550 mm and a mean annual temperature of 11.9-12.4°C. The soils are
82 calcixerepts developed on a quaternary calcareous glaxis with less than 5% slope.

83 The area was reforested between 1958 and 1969 with a mixture of the non-native *Pinus nigra*
84 Arnold subsp. *nigra* and the native *P. nigra* subsp. *salzmannii* Franco. Formerly, it was
85 cultivated with cereal crops. Scattered adult *Q. ilex* and *Quercus faginea* Lam. form a lower
86 tree layer. These oaks already existed before the plantation, in the field boundaries.

87 In March 2000, an experimental silvicultural treatment was executed with the aim of
88 improving the habitat for *T. melanosporum* fruiting (Reyna *et al.*, 2004). Circular canopy
89 openings were created around the truffle-producing grounds by systematically cutting down
90 all the pines and removing the shrubs. Woody coarse debris were chipped and spread
91 throughout the opening. Adult oaks were retained and slightly pruned.

92 When the treatment was executed, the density of adult pines ranged from 1000 to 2450 trees
93 ha⁻¹, with Assman top height from 9 to 12 m; the density of adult *Quercus* ranged from 29 to
94 259 trees ha⁻¹, with 62% *Q. ilex* and 38% *Q. faginea*; and the understorey shrubs (*Juniperus*
95 sp. pl., *Prunus spinosa* L, *Quercus coccifera* L and *Genista* sp. pl.) and herbs cover was low
96 (Table 1).

97

98 2.2 Data collection

99 Tree regeneration (height<130 cm) was measured in ten canopy openings created in 2000 in
100 the matrix of the pine plantation. The opening was settled as an expanded gap, with its
101 borderline delimited by the trunks of the trees bordering the gap. The openings were sampled
102 one year after the treatment execution, and again the second year, the fourth and the fifth.

103 The height and crown surface area were recorded for all the tree regeneration in the opening.

104 The regeneration of *Q. ilex* and *Q. faginea* was classified as recent acorn seedlings (with the
105 acorn or cotyledon scatters still attached) or seedling resprouts (individuals subject to
106 recurrent cycles of shoot dieback and resprouting). The origin of the latter (root sprout or
107 acorn) was not discerned, as the seedlings were not dug up. The oak regeneration coming
108 from stump resprouts of adult trees was excluded from data analysis; they accounted for less
109 than 0.4% of all the sampled individuals. In young *P. nigra* seedlings, subspecies were not
110 distinguished.

111 The density of regeneration of *Q. ilex*, *Q. faginea* and *P. nigra* was computed. For *Q. ilex*, the
112 percent soil covered by the regeneration was also calculated, as well as the median height of
113 the individuals. The median was preferred instead of the mean because the height of *Q. ilex*
114 shoots followed a lognormal distribution and a logarithmic transformation was performed.
115 The median height of *Q. faginea* and *P. nigra* was not calculated, because in most plots there
116 were less than 30 individuals.

117 The following characteristics of the forest stand and the canopy openings were determined
118 from fieldwork and aerial photographs (Table 1): site index (Assman top height of *P. nigra*
119 subsp. *salzmannii* at the age of 60 was estimated using site index curves from Gómez-Loranca,
120 1996), pre-treatment canopy cover, residual BA in the opening (in which *Q. ilex* and *Q.*
121 *faginea* were the only trees) as an estimate of shading and competition from residual adult
122 trees, the size of the canopy opening (edge effect is higher in smaller-sized gaps) and the
123 relative abundance of the allochthonous *P. nigra* subsp. *nigra* in the dominant tree layer
124 around the openings (in which *P. nigra* and *P. salzmannii* accounted for 95% of the trees).
125 A control plot was sampled in the matrix of pine plantation surrounding each canopy opening.
126 Each control consisted of three square subplots of 400 m², randomly located around the
127 opening, at a distance of 5-10 m from the borderline. The plots were sampled in 2001 and
128 again in 2007.

129

130 2.3 Statistical analysis

131 An information-theoretic approach (Burnham and Anderson, 2002) was used to assess the
132 time trend of tree regeneration after the opening and the influence of forest stand
133 characteristics. For the analysis of *Q. ilex* and *Q. faginea* regeneration, a set of 32 models was
134 developed that included all the combinations of the following predictor variables: time from
135 treatment, site index, pre-treatment canopy cover, post-treatment BA and opening size. Since
136 *P. nigra* does not regenerate through advance regeneration, in the analysis of *P. nigra*
137 regeneration pre-treatment canopy cover was excluded; the relative abundance of *P. nigra*
138 subsp. *nigra* was included instead to assess regeneration differences between the two
139 subspecies.

140 These a priori models were constructed with linear mixed models (LMM) in which time was
141 included as a repeated measures variable, stand characteristics were included as fixed
142 predictors and an unstructured covariance matrix was specified (SPSS, 2006). The response
143 variables were log transformed when the model assumptions were violated, as well as time
144 from treatment.

145 In the various analyses performed, none of the competing models was strongly supported as
146 the best ($w_i > 0.9$), so model averaging was employed to account for model selection
147 uncertainty (Burnham and Anderson, 2002). The following statistics are provided for
148 inference: the model-averaged parameter estimate, which shows the direction of a predictor
149 effect on the response; its 90% confidence interval (CI); and the sum of the Akaike weights
150 (Σw_i), which indicates the relative importance of a predictor. Predictor variables were
151 considered important in explaining variation in the response when the CI did not overlap zero
152 and Σw_i approached one. The best models from each set (with the lower Kullback-Liebler
153 distance to the observed data) are also provided (Supplementary Tables S1, S2).
154 The characteristics of *Q. ilex* and *Q. faginea* seedling bank in the control pine stand were also
155 assessed with an information-theoretic approach. The following predictors were tested: time
156 (sampling of 2001 vs. 2007), site index, canopy cover, and BA of adult *Quercus* (which grow
157 in the lower tree layer).

158 A post-hoc analysis was conducted to explore the time trend of *Q. faginea* regeneration
159 density. The width of the rings of dominant *P. nigra* subsp. *salzmannii* (20 trees distributed
160 throughout the study site) was used as a proxy for the effect of weather on trees (Martín-
161 Benito et al., 2008).

162

163 3 Results

164 3.1 Density of *Q. ilex* regeneration

165 In the canopy openings, model averaging indicated that time from treatment was the only
166 predictor whose effect on the density of *Q. ilex* regeneration was clearly supported by the data
167 (the 90% CI did not overlap zero) while showing a high relative importance (Σw_i). The
168 relation was positive (Table 2) and resulted in a rather linear increase during the five years
169 after treatment (Fig. 1a).

170 In the control pine stand, model averaging of *Q. ilex* regeneration density indicated that time
171 was the only predictor with both a 90% CI not overlapping zero and a high Σw_i (Tables 3, 4).
172 Canopy cover showed a moderate positive influence on the density (Table 4).

173 Seedling resprouts were the only regeneration type present in the openings one year after
174 treatment, whereas in the fifth year they were 14 times more abundant than recent acorn
175 seedlings. In the control pine stand, seedling resprouts of *Q. ilex* accounted for almost all the
176 individuals in 2001, and they were 6 times more abundant than recent acorn seedlings in 2007.

177

178 3.2 Density of *Q. faginea* regeneration

179 In the openings, none of the predictors used in the model averaging showed both a 90% CI
180 not overlapping zero and a high Σw_i . However, time from treatment and site index showed a
181 moderate positive influence on the density of *Q. faginea* regeneration, and post-treatment BA
182 showed a moderate negative influence (Table 2, Fig. 1a).

183 Since time did not show a strong and straightforward effect on *Q. faginea* regeneration
184 density (Fig. 1a), a post-hoc analysis was conducted to compare three different time patterns:
185 linear, quadratic and related to *P. nigra* ring width. Ring width reached a much lower value of
186 Akaike's information criterion (AIC=14.6) than the linear (32.0) and the quadratic (41.3) time
187 trends, indicating a better fit.

188 In the pine plantation, model averaging of *Q. faginea* regeneration density indicated that time
189 was the only predictor with both a 90% CI not overlapping zero and a high Σw_i (Tables 3, 4).
190 Seedling resprouts were the only regeneration type found in the openings one year after
191 treatment, whereas in the fifth year they were 15 times more abundant than recent acorn
192 seedlings. In the pine stand, seedling resprouts of *Q. faginea* accounted for almost all the
193 individuals in 2001, and they were 31 times more abundant than recent acorn seedlings in
194 2007.

195

196 3.3 Density of *P. nigra* regeneration

197 Model averaging of *P. nigra* seedling density in the openings revealed that relative abundance
198 of adult *P. nigra* subsp *nigra* around the opening, opening size and site index showed a 90%
199 CI not overlapping zero while having a high Σw_i . The effect of the two former on the density
200 of *P. nigra* regeneration was negative, while the effect of the latter was positive (Table 5).

201 Five years after the opening only 9% of the seedlings were two or three years old and the rest
202 were one year old. In the pine plantation, none of the seedlings found (Table 3) was more than
203 three years old.

204

205 3.4 Height of *Q. ilex* regeneration

206 Model averaging of *Q. ilex* median height in the openings revealed that time from treatment,
207 site index, pre-treatment canopy cover and post-treatment BA presented both a 90% CI not
208 overlapping zero and a high Σw_i (Table 2). Time showed a positive relation with the median
209 height of *Q. ilex* regeneration, with an apparent curvilinear pattern reflecting an increase that
210 levelled off with time (Fig. 1b). Site index showed a positive effect, whereas the effect of pre-
211 treatment canopy cover and post-treatment BA was negative. The increase in height from the

212 fourth to the fifth year after treatment did not show a negative correlation with the density of
213 *Q. ilex* regeneration in the fourth year (Pearson's $r=0.59$; 90% CI: 0.06, 0.86).

214 Model averaging of *Q. ilex* median height in the pine stand indicated that time was the only
215 predictor with both a 90% CI not overlapping zero and a high Σw_i , with median height being
216 lower in 2007 than in 2001 (Tables 3, 4).

217 On average 8.3 individuals ha^{-1} recruited into the adult stratum (height>130 cm) between the
218 first and the fifth year after the canopy opening, which account for 1.5% of the seedling
219 resprouts found in the first year. In the pine stand, only one individual of *Q. ilex* regeneration
220 recruited into the adult stratum in the ten plots between 2001 and 2007, whereas five
221 individuals reduced their height from above to below 130 cm.

222

223 3.5 Soil cover by *Q. ilex* regeneration

224 In the openings, model averaging indicated that time from treatment was the only predictor
225 with both a 90% CI not overlapping zero and a high Σw_i (Table 2). Its relation with the
226 percent soil cover by *Q. ilex* regeneration was positive, and resulted in an apparently linear
227 increase during the five years after treatment (Fig. 1b).

228 In the pine stand, model averaging of the soil cover by *Q. ilex* regeneration indicated that time
229 was the only predictor with both a 90% CI not overlapping zero and a high Σw_i (Tables 3, 4).

230

231 4 Discussion

232 Canopy disturbance usually triggers a period of rapid change in the vegetation. During this
233 stand initiation stage it is usually difficult to accurately predict changes, although of high
234 interest because future stand characteristics are highly influenced by the initial stage (Johnson
235 *et al.*, 2002).

236 In our study site the canopy openings were created in the matrix of a 31-42 year-old *P. nigra*
237 plantation with high density and a sparse lower tree layer of oaks. No established *P. nigra*
238 regeneration was found under this canopy. Lucas-Borja *et al.* (2011) found that BA ranging
239 25-40 $\text{m}^2 \text{ha}^{-1}$ (similar to those in our study site, Table 1) are optimum for the emergence of *P.*
240 *nigra* subsp. *salzmannii* seedlings in Central Spain, although Gómez-Aparicio *et al.* (2006)
241 showed the negative effect of shade on seedling biomass. Tíscar-Oliver (2007) found that
242 seedling survival is highly dependent on the first summer drought.

243 By contrast, *Q. ilex* regeneration was relatively abundant under the pine canopy, and its
244 density was of the same order of magnitude than that found by Ruiz-Benito *et al.* (2012) in
245 Spanish *P. nigra* plantations and by Gómez-Aparicio *et al.* (2009) in pine plantations in

246 southern Spain, although much lower than the density found by Gracia *et al.* (2001) in *Q. ilex*
247 coppice stands of northeastern Spain. In southern Spain, Urbieta *et al.* (2011) found that *Q.*
248 *ilex* regeneration was much more abundant in oak than in pine forests, although the maximum
249 was obtained in mixed stands.

250 European jays abundantly disperse *Quercus* acorns in pine stands (Gómez, 2003). However,
251 seedling resprouts were much more frequent than young acorn seedlings. *Q. ilex* regeneration
252 was small-sized and no evidences of a clear positive time trend in height growth were found.
253 These are characteristic features of oak species that form seedling banks and perpetuate
254 through repeated shoot dieback and resprout (Johnson *et al.*, 2002).

255 After the canopy opening *Q. ilex* was also the most abundant tree regeneration. The scarcity
256 of recent acorn seedlings indicates the dominant role that the advance regeneration played in
257 forest dynamics during the first years after the opening. Recruitment of new acorn seedling
258 was also observed, but the survival of young *Q. ilex* seedlings in full sunlight is usually low
259 (Marañón *et al.*, 2004; Prévosto *et al.*, 2011b) and therefore it is difficult to predict if they will
260 increase the density of *Q. ilex* meaningfully.

261 *Q. ilex* is considered as intermediate in shade tolerance (Valladares and Niinemets, 2008),
262 with seedling recruitment and early survival being higher under full canopy than in full
263 sunlight. In our pine stands, the canopy cover positively related to the density of *Q. ilex*
264 regeneration. The harvesting operations and the sudden exposition to full sunlight may have
265 hampered the survival of some young seedlings and seedling resprouts with low root reserves
266 (Dillaway *et al.*, 2007). However, after the opening the density of *Q. ilex* regeneration
267 increased linearly with time, indicating the vigour of the advance regeneration to resprout and
268 survive in full light.

269 Retana *et al.* (1999) and Marañón *et al.* (2004) pointed out that, despite its shade tolerance, *Q.*
270 *ilex* seedlings are unlikely to grow into saplings with low light levels. Gómez-Aparicio *et al.*
271 (2009) found that in southern Spain the recruitment of *Q. ilex* seedlings was at maximum at
272 pine densities similar to those in our study site, whereas the density of saplings was maximum
273 at lower densities. In a *Pinus halepensis* Mill. shelterwood in southern France, Prévosto *et al.*
274 (2011a) found that the growth of sown *Q. ilex* was higher in the stands with lower BA (10 m²
275 ha⁻¹). We observed an important increase in the height of *Q. ilex* regeneration in the years
276 immediately after the canopy opening, whereas in the pine plantation no evidences of a clear
277 height increase were found during the same period of time. This indicates that under the pine
278 canopy there were *Q. ilex* seedling resprouts that retained the ability to grow rapidly after
279 release, in contrast to the lack of response reported by Gracia *et al.* (2001) in thinned coppice

280 forests. This tends to support the view that at least part of the seedling resprouts is able to
281 recruit into the adult stratum when they are released.

282 However, the evolution of *Q. ilex* median height suggests a reduction in the growth rate of the
283 regeneration over time. This reduction is not apparently related to intraspecific competition
284 among seedling resprouts, since the density of regeneration was low and the correlation
285 between density and height increase was not negative. Another factor which could influence
286 height growth in small openings is the edge effect; however in our openings the size did not
287 appear to be as important as the other predictors. This could be an effect of the narrow range
288 of this variable (Table 1): York *et al.* (2003) studied group selection cuttings with a larger
289 range of sizes (0.1-1 ha) in California and found that opening size was positively related to
290 seedling height growth.

291 Another factor frequently affecting the behaviour of oak advance regeneration is the
292 competition of the understorey shrubs (Johnson *et al.*, 2002). However, in our study site the
293 development of the understorey was moderate (Table 1). This is probably related to the
294 former agricultural use and to the high stand density of the pine stand, although under the
295 Continental-Mediterranean climate of central Spain the density of the woody understorey is
296 usually low (Costa *et al.*, 1996).

297 On the other hand, the canopy cover before treatment and the residual (post-treatment) BA of
298 adult oaks negatively related to the height of *Q. ilex* regeneration. The residual BA of adult
299 oaks showed a negative effect despite being always lower than 2.5 m² ha⁻¹. Gracia *et al.* (2001)
300 found that in thinned *Q. ilex* coppice forests with BA 15-17.5 m² ha⁻¹ the growth of *Q. ilex*
301 seedlings was suppressed. This suppressive effect could be caused by shading, root
302 competition or topsoil properties (Puerta-Piñero *et al.*, 2006). The negative influence of the
303 canopy cover before treatment agrees with the results of Dillaway *et al.* (2007), where the
304 light levels under close canopy positively related to the root diameter and reserves of *Quercus*
305 *alba* L advance regeneration, the latter being related to the vigour of advance regeneration.
306 This suggests that a previous thinning of the pines could have improved the growth of
307 seedling resprouts after opening.

308 In the case of *Q. faginea* the advance regeneration also played an important role in the
309 openings. In contrast with *Q. ilex*, the increase in *Q. faginea* density was not as steady, and it
310 was moderately influenced by site index and by the residual adult oaks. This suggests a less
311 vigorous resprouting and survival of seedling resprouts in full sunlight. *Q. faginea* is a semi-
312 deciduous species that exhibits biological features similar to those of *Q. ilex*, but it is
313 considered more sensitive to drought (Sanz-Pérez *et al.*, 2007). The fact that the increase in

314 the density of *Q. faginea* regeneration in the openings was better explained by annual weather
315 conditions than by time from treatment supports this view.

316 The regeneration of *P. nigra* did not establish for the moment in the openings, and the
317 emergence of seedlings was influenced by site index. This limitation in the effective
318 recruitment is similar to the difficulties in regeneration after wildfire and clearcutting
319 encountered for *P. nigra* subsp. *salzmannii* in Spain, where this taxon is considered quite
320 shade-tolerant compared to other native Spanish pines (Ordóñez *et al.*, 2004; Tíscar-Oliver,
321 2007).

322 On the other hand, *P. nigra* subsp. *nigra* has been traditionally considered as shade-intolerant,
323 although Chauchard *et al.* (2006) found that it did not behaved as such in southeastern France.
324 In Spain we know of no study about its shade tolerance. Due to the high mortality of young *P.*
325 *nigra* seedlings, we could not determine which taxon they belonged to. However, the negative
326 relation of seedling density in the openings with the abundance of adult *P. nigra* subsp. *nigra*
327 around the openings suggests that the emerging seedlings were mostly *P. nigra* subsp.
328 *salzmannii*.

329 The current lack of effective regeneration of *P. nigra* in the openings does not necessarily
330 involve the loss of pines in the medium term. In burned Mediterranean pine forests, Gracia *et*
331 *al.* (2002) observed that *P. nigra* subsp. *salzmannii* regenerated abundantly only after the
332 resprouting *Q. faginea* covered the soil (from the 4th to the 15th year), and in the 37th year
333 pines dominated the tree layer, pointing to a nurse effect. In our study site, the soil cover by *Q.*
334 *ilex* is low five years after the opening (Fig. 1b), so a long-term monitoring would be
335 necessary to discern if *P. nigra* establishment is restricted by site conditions or by the scarce
336 canopy cover.

337 Our results show that the canopy opening triggered a response in *Q. ilex* advance regeneration.
338 However, since the monitoring suggests a reduction in median height growth over time, the
339 effective recruitment of *Q. ilex* into the dominant tree layer will depend on the proportion of
340 seedling resprouts capable of maintaining a competitive height growth in the new conditions.
341 Our results also suggest that the stand density before treatment and the stand density of oaks
342 after treatment are detrimental to the height growth of this regeneration.

343 The management objective in the study site was to achieve an open oak-dominated stand
344 around the truffle-producing grounds in order to improve the habitat for *T. melanosporum*
345 fructification. The size of the openings was kept to the minimum necessary in order to
346 enhance the compatible management of truffle and other forest uses (Reyna *et al.*, 2004). In
347 canopy openings with sizes ranging 0.17-0.43 ha we did not find clear evidences that the

348 opening size hindered the release of *Q. ilex* seedling resprouts; and *Q. ilex* regeneration
349 enjoyed a competitive advantage over *P. nigra*. The statistical models predict that soil cover
350 by *Q. ilex* regeneration will be on average 4% in the 10th year and 8% in the 20th year. This
351 will add to the canopy cover of residual adult oaks, which was on average 12% one year after
352 the opening and 13% in the fourth year. Soil cover by *Q. ilex* will likely remain below 30% in
353 the short term, thus suitable for *T. melanosporum* production (Reyna *et al.*, 2004) without
354 additional silvicultural operations.

355

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362

363 Supplementary data

364 Table S1. 90% confidence set of best-ranked LMM models for tree regeneration
365 characteristics in the canopy openings.

366 Table S2. 90% confidence set of best-ranked LMM models for tree regeneration
367 characteristics in the control pine stand.

368

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452 **Table 1.** Summary statistics for the canopy openings monitored and the control pine stands
 453 (SD: standard deviation)

	Mean (SD)	Range
Canopy openings		
Site index (Assman top height of <i>P. nigra</i> at age 60, in m)	16.4 (1.8)	13.6-19.6
Pre-treatment canopy cover (%)	88 (11)	69-99
Size of canopy opening (m ²)	2330 (829)	1700-4300
Basal area of residual <i>Quercus</i> (m ² ha ⁻¹)	1.55 (0.62)	0.44-2.49
Canopy cover of residual <i>Quercus</i> (%)	12 (5)	5-20
Shrub cover (%)	4 (2)	1-5
Herb cover (%)	8 (8)	2-30
Relative abundance of <i>P. nigra</i> subsp. <i>nigra</i> in the pine stand adjacent to opening (%)	57.8 (25.9)	5.2-100
Control pine stand (in 2001)		
Canopy cover (%)	78 (9)	58-92
<i>Pinus nigra</i> basal area (m ² ha ⁻¹)	40 (6)	28-51
<i>Quercus</i> basal area (m ² ha ⁻¹)	0.88 (0.74)	0.01-2.19
Shrub cover (%)	2 (4)	0.3-12
Herb cover (%)	8 (5)	1-17

454

455 **Table 2.** Statistics used for inference on the characteristics of *Quercus* regeneration in the
 456 openings: model-averaged parameter estimates and their 90% confidence intervals (CI), and
 457 relative importance of each predictor (Σw_i). SI: site index, BApost: post-treatment basal area,
 458 CCpre: pre-treatment canopy cover, Size: size of the opening.

	Time ¹	SI	CCpre	BApost	Size
<i>Quercus ilex</i> density ²					
Parameter estimate	0.0060	-0.059	0.0157	0.29	0.55
90% CI - lower	0.0053	-0.139	0.0060	0.10	-0.79
90% CI - upper	0.0067	0.022	0.0254	0.48	1.89
Σw_i	1.00	0.05	0.01	0.17	0.38
<i>Quercus faginea</i> density ²					
Parameter estimate	0.0085	0.33	0.0088	-1.07	1.13
90% CI - lower	0.0070	0.14	-0.0186	-1.85	-3.27
90% CI - upper	0.0100	0.52	0.0363	-0.29	5.53
Σw_i	0.45	0.36	0.01	0.44	0.73
<i>Quercus ilex</i> height					
Parameter estimate	19.9	1.67	-0.61	-2.04	5.6
90% CI - lower	17.8	1.10	-0.70	-3.40	-6.4
90% CI - upper	21.9	2.25	-0.51	-0.68	17.6
Σw_i	1.00	0.90	0.90	0.83	0.54
Soil cover by <i>Quercus ilex</i> ²					
Parameter estimate	0.95	0.138	0.0157	0.191	1.59
90% CI - lower	0.79	0.071	0.0032	-0.079	-0.18
90% CI - upper	1.11	0.205	0.0282	0.462	3.36
Σw_i	1.00	0.27	0.01	0.19	0.57

459 ¹ Time was log-transformed for the analysis of *Q. ilex* height and soil cover

460 ² Variable log transformed

461

462 **Table 3.** Summary statistics for the tree regeneration in the control pine stand (SD: standard
 463 deviation)

	Sampling 2001		Sampling 2007	
	Mean (SD)	Range	Mean (SD)	Range
<i>Quercus ilex</i> density (ha ⁻¹)	1609 (673)	683-2425	2979 (1170)	1333- 5125
<i>Quercus ilex</i> height (cm)	15 (3)	10-20	14 (2)	10-18
<i>Quercus ilex</i> soil cover (%)	0.67 (0.39)	0.03-1.23	1.92 (1.39)	0.22-5.05
<i>Quercus faginea</i> density (ha ⁻¹)	216 (120)	75-492	651 (310)	158-1067
<i>Pinus nigra</i> density (ha ⁻¹)	0	0	361 (410)	8-925

464

465 **Table 4.** Statistics used for inference on the characteristics of the *Quercus* seedling bank in
 466 the control pine stand: model-averaged parameter estimates and their 90% confidence
 467 intervals (CI), and relative importance of each predictor (Σw_i). SI: site index, CC: canopy
 468 cover, BA-Qu: basal area of adult *Quercus* (which grow in the lower tree layer).

	Time ¹	SI	CC	BA-Qu
<i>Quercus ilex</i> density ²				
Parameter estimate	0.0036	-0.0122	0.0111	-0.0072
90% CI - lower	0.0031	-0.0457	0.0059	-0.0549
90% CI - upper	0.0041	0.0213	0.0163	0.0405
Σw_i	1.00	0.04	0.56	0.04
<i>Quercus faginea</i> density ²				
Parameter estimate	0.0068	0.059	0.0055	0.083
90% CI - lower	0.0057	0.005	-0.0045	0.003
90% CI - upper	0.0078	0.112	0.0156	0.164
Σw_i	1.00	0.21	0.01	0.26
<i>Quercus ilex</i> height				
Parameter estimate	-1.40	0.59	0.043	0.49
90% CI - lower	-2.23	-0.01	-0.069	-0.42
90% CI - upper	-0.57	1.19	0.155	1.40
Σw_i	0.97	0.68	0.11	0.56
Soil cover by <i>Quercus ilex</i> ²				
Parameter estimate	0.0073	0.075	0.0165	0.114
90% CI - lower	0.0061	-0.009	0.0017	-0.010
90% CI - upper	0.0086	0.160	0.0312	0.238
Σw_i	1.00	0.19	0.07	0.27

469 ¹ Time was log-transformed for the analysis of *Q. ilex* height and soil cover

470 ² Variable log transformed

471

472 **Table 5.** Statistics used for inference on the density of *Pinus nigra* regeneration (log
 473 transformed for the analysis) in the openings: model-averaged parameter estimates and their
 474 90% confidence intervals (CI), and relative importance of each predictor variable. SI: site
 475 index, PNN: relative abundance of *Pinus nigra* subsp. *nigra* in the adjacent pine stand,
 476 BApost: post-treatment basal area, Size: size of the opening.

	Time	SI	PNN	BApost	Size
Parameter estimate	0.0155	0.34	-3.21	-0.20	-2.206
90% CI - lower	0.0073	0.20	-4.60	-0.81	-4.403
90% CI - upper	0.0238	0.48	-1.82	0.41	-0.009
Σw_i	0.02	0.77	0.97	0.16	0.77

477

478

479

480 **Figure 1.** Mean density of tree regeneration (a), median height of *Quercus ilex* regeneration
 481 and soil covered by *Quercus ilex* regeneration (b). Error bars represent standard deviation
 482 (n=10)

483

484 **Supplementary Table S1.** 90% confidence set of best-ranked LMM models examining the
485 characteristics of tree regeneration after the canopy opening. k: no. of parameters in the LMM,
486 Ti: time from treatment, SI: site index, CCpre: pre-treatment canopy cover, BApost: post-
487 treatment basal area, Size: size of the opening, PNN: relative abundance of *Pinus nigra* subsp.
488 *nigra* in the adjacent pine stand.

Candidate models	k	AIC _c ¹	ΔAIC _c ¹	w _i ¹	w _{best} /w _i ¹
<i>Quercus ilex</i> density ²					
Ti	13	-42.9	-	0.49	-
Ti+Size	14	-42.0	0.9	0.31	1.6
Ti+BApost	14	-39.7	3.2	0.10	4.9
Ti+BApost+Size	15	-38.2	4.8	0.05	10.8
<i>Quercus faginea</i> density ²					
Size	13	41.4	-	0.21	-
Ti+Size	14	41.5	0.1	0.19	1.1
SI+BApost+Size	15	42.4	1.0	0.13	1.7
Ti+SI+BApost+Size	16	43.3	2.0	0.08	2.7
SI+BApost	14	43.8	2.4	0.06	3.3
Ti	13	44.0	2.6	0.06	3.7
BApost+Size	14	44.1	2.8	0.05	4.0
Null model	12	44.2	2.8	0.05	4.1
Ti+SI+BApost	15	44.3	2.9	0.05	4.3
Ti+BApost+Size	15	44.7	3.3	0.04	5.2
<i>Pinus nigra</i> density ²					
SI+PNN+Size	15	113.0	-	0.52	-
SI+PNN	14	116.0	3.0	0.11	4.6
SI+PNN+BApost+Size	16	116.2	3.3	0.10	5.1
PNN+Size	14	116.5	3.5	0.09	5.8
PNN	13	117.0	4.0	0.07	7.4
PNN+BApost+Size	15	119.6	6.6	0.02	27.5
<i>Quercus ilex</i> height					
Ti ² +SI+CCpre+BApost	16	200.3	-	0.43	-
Ti ² +SI+CCpre+BApost+Size	17	200.7	0.4	0.35	1.2
Ti ² +SI+CCpre+Size	16	203.6	3.4	0.08	5.3
Ti ² +Size	14	205.4	5.2	0.03	13.2
Ti ² +BApost+Size	15	205.5	5.3	0.03	13.8
Soil cover by <i>Quercus ilex</i> ²					
Ti ² +Size	14	-22.4	-	0.36	-
Ti ²	13	-21.1	1.3	0.19	1.9
Ti ² +SI	14	-20.7	1.7	0.15	2.4
Ti ² +SI+Size	15	-19.8	2.6	0.10	3.7
Ti ² +BApost+Size	15	-19.8	2.6	0.10	3.7
Ti ² +BApost	14	-19.2	3.2	0.07	4.9

489 ¹ The models are ranked according to the Akaike's information criterion corrected for small
490 sample size (AIC_c) and compared according to Akaike weights (w_i), which indicate the
491 likelihood of a model to be the best in the set. The 90% confidence set of models was
492 identified by cumulatively summing w_i of the highest-ranked models. The relative strength of
493 the best model versus other models was assessed through evidence ratios (w_{best}/w_i), which
494 provide a measure of how much more likely the best model is than model i .

495 ² Variable log transformed

496

497 **Supplementary Table S2.** 90% confidence set of best-ranked LMM models examining the
 498 characteristics of the *Quercus* seedling bank in the control pine stand. k: no. of parameters in
 499 the LMM, Ti: time, SI: site index, CC: canopy cover, BA-Qu: basal area of adult *Quercus*
 500 (which grow in the lower tree layer), PNN: relative abundance of *Pinus nigra* subsp. *nigra* in
 501 the adjacent pine stand.

Candidate models	k	AIC _c ¹	ΔAIC _c ¹	w _i ¹	w _{best} /w _i ¹
<i>Quercus ilex</i> density ²					
Ti + CC	7	-18.9	-	0.52	-
Ti	6	-18.4	0.5	0.40	1.3
<i>Quercus faginea</i> density ²					
Ti	6	45.5	-	0.61	-
Ti + BA-Qu	7	48.0	2.5	0.17	3.5
Ti + ATH	7	48.7	3.2	0.12	4.9
<i>Quercus ilex</i> height					
Ti ² + SI + BA-Qu	8	293.0	-	0.35	-
Ti ² + SI	7	293.7	0.7	0.25	1.4
Ti ² + BA-Qu	7	294.9	1.9	0.14	2.6
Ti ²	6	295.0	2.0	0.13	2.7
Ti ² + SI + CC + BA-Qu	9	297.6	4.6	0.03	10.2
Soil cover by <i>Quercus ilex</i> ²					
Ti ²	6	80.0	-	0.55	-
Ti ² + BA-Qu	7	82.2	2.1	0.19	2.9
Ti ² + SI	7	83.1	3.1	0.12	4.6
Ti ² + SI + BA-Qu	8	84.3	4.3	0.06	8.7

502 ¹ The models are ranked according to the AIC_c and compared according to w_i, which indicate
 503 the likelihood of a model to be the best in the set. The 90% confidence set of models was
 504 identified by cumulatively summing the highest w_i. The ratios w_{best}/w_i provide a measure of
 505 how much more likely the best model is than model i.

506 ² Variable log transformed

507